

Boundary layer receptivity to free-stream turbulence and discrete roughness elements

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The receptivity of a two-dimensional boundary layer flow developing on a flat plate with a super-elliptical leading edge to incoming disturbances in the presence of a discrete roughness element (DRE) is studied by direct numerical simulation. The DRE is a truncated cylinder with height k and fixed diameter. Its height is varied to cover a parameter space defined by the ratio of the element height to the local boundary layer displacement thickness k/δ^* and the Reynolds number based on the element height, Re_{kk} . Under the conditions simulated, in the absence of externally-imposed disturbances, steady flows are recovered. Two sources of disturbances are then considered: a localized volumetric forcing analogous to a suction/blowing strip that introduces plane monochromatic Tollmien-Schlichting (T-S) waves upstream of the DRE, and synthetic isotropic free-stream turbulence (FST) imposed as an inlet condition upstream of the leading edge. Two different dimensionless temporal frequencies of the T-S waves, $F = 90 \times 10^{-6}$ ($\omega = 0.21$) and $F = 120 \times 10^{-6}$ ($\omega = 0.29$), and two DRE heights, $k = 0.3\delta^*$ ($Re_{kk} = 50$) and $k = 0.5\delta^*$ ($Re_{kk} = 138$), are analysed to cover different receptivity scenarios. The instantaneous perturbation fields for each test case are presented and assessed through the analysis of the evolution of the envelopes of the resulting disturbances. The DNS simulations showed a good agreement with the PSE analysis of the flow instabilities of the case without roughness element. In the cases including a DRE, the element with $k = 0.3\delta^*$ ($Re_{kk} = 50$) does not have a meaningful impact on the stability of the perturbation field; while the DRE with $k = 0.5\delta^*$ ($Re_{kk} = 138$) is a destabilizing agent of the perturbations for the T-S cases and is a stabilizer of the flow in the presence of FST.

I. Introduction

IN the search of the aviation industry for more efficient aircraft that reduce fuel consumption, reduce the carbon footprint of commercial flights, and make every airplane more sustainable, the improvement in aerodynamic efficiency is a key goal that can be achieved by minimizing the aerodynamic drag of the wings. In this sense, the most important contribution to aerodynamic drag is produced by skin friction due to turbulent flow. Hence, special efforts are put into the delay or suppression of the processes that lead to the flow transition to turbulence, increasing the fraction of the wing surface that is under laminar flow conditions. The design of such natural laminar flow strategies requires a deep understanding of the complete physical processes that lead to transition. Following Morkovin [1], the relevant laminar-turbulent transition scenarios in boundary layer flows are initiated with the penetration or inception of flow disturbances within the boundary layer, in a process named receptivity. This can occur through wall imperfections (discontinuities or roughness), leading-edge curvature, vibrations, free-stream disturbances that impinge the aerodynamic surface, and generally via a combination of two or more of them. The receptivity process determines the nature, spatial structure and amplitude of the initial boundary-layer disturbances, prior to their amplification by hydrodynamic instability mechanisms.

The receptivity of two-dimensional boundary layers in incompressible flows has received continuous attention for several decades, as it constitutes the simplest configuration of relevance to transition on wings. Modal instability in two-dimensional boundary layers under favorable and moderately-adverse pressure gradients is dominated by Tollmien-Schlichting (T-S) waves. Their relatively small growth rates result in a linear growth phase that may extend over a significant portion of the airfoil before non-linear phenomena become relevant, which explains the broad success of transition prediction methods based on the accumulated amplification, like the e-to-the-N method[2, 3], for this kind

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of flows. However, despite of the relatively simple linear amplification phase, these methods rely on experimental calibration of the transition N-factor to account for the impact of free-stream turbulence intensity, wall roughness and other aspects related to receptivity.

With the aim of minimizing the impact of surface discontinuities in flat-plate experiments, Lin et al. [4] introduced the so-called “modified super-elliptic leading edge” geometry which results in a smooth continuous surface joining the leading edge to the plate with zero curvature at the joint. They used this geometry to study experimentally the receptivity to externally-controlled acoustic disturbances. For the same geometry, [5] or [6] did numerical analyses of the receptivity to inflow disturbances of different types. The latter analyzed the boundary-layer receptivity to three-dimensional vortical perturbations, triggering a streaky pattern of the disturbance streamwise velocity inside the boundary layer for the zero-frequency streamwise vorticity, and getting T-S modes for the high-frequency spanwise vorticity modes.

While the receptivity process is significantly weaker, it is recognized that free-stream turbulence can penetrate in the boundary layer even in the absence of wall discontinuities, irregularities or vibration, due to its weak non-parallelism. Jacobs and Durbin [7] or Brandt et al. [8], went further in the modeling of the inlet perturbations and studied the transition of boundary layers after imposing isotropic free-stream turbulence at the inlet boundary, where the turbulence intensity and the turbulence integral length scale are used as control parameters. In both works the turbulent inflow is constructed using the continuous spectrum of the linearized Navier-Stokes equations [9], together with analytical models of the turbulent kinetic energy spectrum.

The receptivity to free-stream disturbances is remarkably increased by the presence of surface imperfections and roughness; early works illustrate that the presence of a discrete roughness element (DRE) of small but comparable size to the local boundary layer thickness can enhance the penetration of external disturbance so as to render the effect of boundary-layer non-parallelism negligible. The experimental work of Plogmann et al. [10] introduced the classification of the roughness elements according to the height of the element k relative to the local displacement thickness δ^* , as small ($k/\delta^* < 0.2$), when they produce linear receptivity with k ; medium ($0.2 < k/\delta^* < 1.0$), that generate non-linear receptivity and a qualitative change in the steady flow topology in the form of a horseshoe-shaped vortex upstream of the roughness element; and large ($k/\delta^* > 1.0$), which produce bypass transition just around or shortly downstream of the roughness element. The numerical study made by Bucci et al. [11] included isotropic free-stream turbulence and studied the effect that several DRE and turbulence parameters have on the dynamics of a two-dimensional incompressible boundary layer over an infinite flat plate. It was concluded that the roughness Reynolds number (Re_{kk}), the aspect ratio of the roughness element (η), the ratio between the roughness height and the boundary layer displacement thickness (k/δ^*), and the free-stream turbulence intensity (Tu) altogether have an impact on the stability and transition of two-dimensional boundary layers. Turbulence intensities between 0.06% and 0.09% produce a meaningful destabilizing effect on the wake of the roughness element. The work by Bucci et al. [11] also proposed the development of a more sophisticated transition diagram than the one proposed by von Doenhoff [12], where only k/δ^* and Re_{kk} are considered. In Weingartner et al. [13] the analysis is focused on a flow visualization study of isolated roughness elements with different η and Re_{kk} . In sub-critical regimes ($Re_{kk} \lesssim 750$) all the aspect ratios produced a varicose (symmetric) disturbance pattern, while it was sinuous (anti-symmetric) in the range of $0.7 \leq \eta \leq 1.2$. The influence of a small discrete roughness element on the evolution of two-dimensional T-S waves was studied experimentally in [14], where a disturbance source is placed upstream of the roughness element. The results showed a weak flow distortion and scattering of the wave into oblique ones for $k/\delta^* = 0.2$ and a quadratic variation of the wave scattering with respect to k for a roughness height well below the displacement thickness.

Most works in the literature that address two-dimensional boundary layers either consider the leading-edge or the discrete roughness element in the presence of incoming vortical disturbances, but not both simultaneously. Further, most works studying the impact of DREs consider either the limit cases of small or large roughness heights, while the range of medium-height elements (k between 20% and 70% of the boundary-layer displacement thickness) is underrepresented in the literature. The combination of synthetic free-stream turbulence and the analysis of its effect on the receptivity in the presence of a leading-edge and a roughness element is also a missing point in the literature. Only the recent work by Vincentiis et al. [15] combines these aspects for a swept-wing case with a three-dimensional boundary layer. Including all these features in the same work could help to give more detail and depth to the transition diagram by Von Doenhoff et al. [12]. This is the objective of the present work.

This work addresses the receptivity analysis of incompressible, nominally two-dimensional boundary layers to free-stream turbulence, discrete roughness elements and their interaction, using direct numerical simulations. The geometry studied is a semi-infinite flat plate with a modified super-ellipse as a leading edge. A cylindrical discrete roughness element is introduced on the flat plate at streamwise locations contained between the first and the second branch of the neutral instability curve for plane T-S waves, and with heights that cover the range from small to large

Fig. 1 General view of the computational domain and mesh, including the DRE (at $x = 115$). The number of elements in the spatial mesh is reduce to ease its visualization.

roughness regimes. Synthetic free-stream turbulence is imposed at the inlet following the methodology proposed by Schlatter [16]. Finally, a volumetric forcing term is used to mimic the effect of a suction/blowing slot or a vibrating ribbon and excite plane T-S waves upstream of the DRE. This methodology allows to study the interaction of different relevant aspects of the receptivity process in the same computational set-up.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II describes the computational geometry, flow configuration, methodology for the generation of the synthetic FST, and the actuator forcing T-S waves. Section III.A presents results for preliminary simulations. The first results are aimed at characterizing the baseline two-dimensional boundary layer flow in the absence of external disturbances and roughness element. This characterization serves to define the location and height of the roughness element and the location of the T-S generator that will be used in subsequent simulations. Section III.B presents calculations done with parabolized stability equations to characterize the instability properties of plane T-S waves developing over the baseline flow, as a previous step to the receptivity analysis. Section III.C shows the validation of the implementation of the free-stream vorticity disturbances and their penetration in the boundary layer, by reproducing results by Schrader et al. [6] for the flat-plate without a roughness element. Finally, section IV summarizes the advances presented in the numerical methodology for the analysis including the illustrative results, and outlines the future research steps.

II. Methodology

Direct numerical simulations (DNS) are carried on using the Spectral Element Method implemented in the open-source code Nek5000 [17], in which the order of the polynomial used to approximate the velocity and pressure fields within each element takes the form $\mathbb{P}_N - \mathbb{P}_{N-2}$, respectively. Unless stated otherwise, the polynomial order is chosen as $N = 7$ for the simulations presented herein. Following the custom practice in hydrodynamic instability, separate simulations are performed for the computation of the base flows (two-dimensional or three-dimensional steady flows) and the three-dimensional linear disturbances developing upon them. Parabolized stability equations (PSE) calculations are also performed to compute the neutral curve for Tollmien-Schlichting (T-S) waves that is used as reference for placing the discrete roughness element.

A. Base geometry and numerical domain

The geometry of interest is shown in figure 1. A semi-infinite flat plate is considered in which the leading edge has the shape of the modified super-ellipse (MSE)

$$\left(\frac{y}{b}\right)^2 = 1 - \left(\frac{a-x}{a}\right)^p, \quad (1)$$

where

$$p = 2 + \left(\frac{x}{a}\right)^2, \quad (2)$$

and a and b are the major and minor semi-axes of the ellipse respectively. The modified super-ellipse reduces the geometrical discontinuity in the junction between the leading edge and the flat plate, with the aim of minimizing

its influence on the boundary layer receptivity to free-stream incoming disturbances. The aspect ratio is taken as $AR \equiv \frac{a}{b} = 6$. The minor semi-axis b is used to non-dimensionalize all lengths throughout the paper.

The downstream length of the computational domain is defined based on the displacement thickness of the two-dimensional boundary layer that develops on the upper side of the flat plate. An initial estimate of the domain length is done assuming the Blasius self-similar solution for a zero-pressure-gradient boundary layer, and obtaining the x -coordinate corresponding to a Reynolds number based on the displacement thickness $Re_{\delta^*} \approx 1100$, which is downstream of the second branch of the neutral curve for T-S waves for most of the relevant frequencies. This estimation is later compared with the actual base flow computation.

B. Base flow computation

Base flow solutions are computed by solving the unsteady incompressible Navier-Stokes equations using Nek5000. Other than the downstream extension, the computational domain mimics the one used by Schrader et al. [6]: to reduce the computational cost, the computational domain used in Nek5000 is shortened in its lower half. The inlet, top and bottom boundaries, that would need to be located at a far distance to accommodate the flow displacement exerted by the solid, are instead truncated at a relatively short distance, as shown in figure 1. Velocity distributions are imposed as Dirichlet conditions at the truncated domain boundaries, that were computed using a numerical simulation on a much larger domain. The minor semi-axis b of the super-ellipse and the free-stream velocity U_∞ are taken as reference quantities for the dimensionless form. The kinematic viscosity is chosen such that the reference Reynolds number $Re_b = U_\infty b / \nu = 2400$.

No slip is imposed at the solid walls, while periodic boundary conditions are set for the spanwise direction. The outlet boundaries have a special treatment, minimizing the dependency of the solution on the length of the lower part and ensuring that the flow field is symmetric over the upper and the lower surface of the flat plate. The solution proposed in [18] solves that issue, as it defines natural boundary conditions at both outlet boundaries, imposing an ambient pressure profile in the lower half. This pressure profile is obtained from the steady base flow obtained for the upper-half of the domain, taking the pressure profile at the same x location as the lower boundary.

C. Isotropic free-stream turbulence

Synthetic free-stream turbulence (FST) is modeled here using a similar procedure to Schlatter [16], which models in-flight or wind-tunnel turbulence conditions described by a prescribed turbulent kinetic energy spectra $E(k)$, where E is the portion of the TKE associated with the spatial wavenumber k . The method is based on the continuous spectrum of vorticity perturbation solutions of the linearized Navier-Stokes equations for uniform flow, which can be written as a superposition of Fourier modes on the three spatial directions and time:

$$\mathbf{u}(x, y, z) = \sum_{\mathbf{k}=(\omega, \gamma, \beta)} A(k) \hat{\mathbf{u}}(\omega, \gamma, \beta) e^{i(\Re\{\alpha(\omega, \gamma, \beta)\}x + \gamma y + \beta z - \omega t)}, \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{u} is the velocity perturbation vector, \mathbf{k} is the wave-vector; α , γ , and β are the wave-numbers in the streamwise, wall-normal and spanwise directions respectively, i.e. $k = \sqrt{\alpha^2 + \beta^2 + \gamma^2}$; ω is the time frequency, $A(k)$ are the amplitudes and $\hat{\mathbf{u}}$ are the normalized eigenfunctions of the continuous spectrum.

The isotropic turbulence is generated by dividing the wavenumber space k into N_s concentric shells. The magnitude of the radius of each of them is the wavevector magnitude k and it is associated to an amplitude within the modeled turbulence spectrum $E(k)$:

$$A(k) = \sqrt{\frac{2E(k)\Delta k}{N_v}}, \quad (4)$$

where Δk defines the discretization of the wavenumber space and N_v is the number of independent vectors of magnitude k considered. In this work, the homogeneity is achieved by picking $N_v = 20$ points regularly distributed as the vertices of a regular dodecahedron, which is increased by adding a second dodecahedron symmetric to the original with respect to the γ -plane. Each dodecahedron is rotated a random angle to ensure that the turbulence is isotropic.

The amplitudes for the chosen wavenumbers match the the von Kármán energy spectrum:

$$E(k) = Tu^2 U_\infty^2 L_I \frac{1.606(kL_I)^4}{(1.350 + (kL_I)^2)^{17/6}}, \quad (5)$$

Fig. 2 Comparison between the spectrum obtained from a synthetic turbulence field and the imposed von Kármán spectrum.

where L_I is the integral length scale, U_∞ is the free-stream velocity and Tu is the turbulent intensity.

In this work, the synthetic FST is imposed as a boundary condition at the inlet and upper and lower boundaries, and considers the turbulent spectrum between $k_{min} = 0.23$ and $k_{max} = 3$, divided in 80 shells, which includes a relevant range of frequencies according to preliminary PSE computations that will be introduced below. The implementation has been validated by comparing the spectrum computed using the synthetic turbulence on a mesh representative of the one used for the flat-plate simulations with the theoretical spectrum (5), as shown in 2. The range of turbulence intensity considered in the study lies between 0% (no inflow FST) and 3%. The integral length scale chosen is $L_I = 2.0$ to ensure that scales with the maximum energy of the von Kármán spectrum lay on the range of the spectrum generated.

D. Discrete roughness element

A cylindrical discrete roughness element (DRE) is added to upper side of the flat plate geometry. Its geometrical features and location are based on the experiments by de Paula et al. [14]. A reference case is considered in which the DRE is located at a streamwise position corresponding to a Reynolds number based on the displacement thickness $Re_{\delta^*} = U_\infty \delta^*(x) / \nu = 920$ and the height of the DRE $k = 0.3\delta^*$. Figure 3 illustrates the geometry and location of the DRE and the computational mesh. Note that the height of the roughness element is largely exaggerated in the figure for the purpose of visualization, as the actual height is $k \ll b$.

Fig. 3 Meshed flat-plate surface including the elliptic leading edge and the DRE. The size of the DRE and its location were modified for visualization purposes.

Fig. 4 Evolution of the Reynolds number based on the displacement thickness Re_{δ^*} along the flat-plate chord.

A matrix of cases is defined by varying the height of the roughness element. Two dimensionless parameters are monitored, namely $Re_{kk} = U_k k / \nu$, where U_k is the flow velocity at the DRE height in the “clean” configuration (i.e. without the roughness element) and the ratio k/δ^* . The DRE heights chosen for this work are within the medium-height range defined in the literature, i.e. $k = 0.3\delta^*$ and $k = 0.5\delta^*$, with $Re_{kk} = 50$ and $Re_{kk} = 138$ respectively.

E. Forced Tollmien-Schlichting waves

Tollmien-Schlichting waves are excited in the flow field with the application of a volumetric forcing term $f(x, y, t)$ applied to the y -momentum equation and given by the expression

$$f(x, y, t) = A_f \cdot \exp\left(-\left(\frac{x - x_c}{s_x}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{y - y_c}{s_y}\right)^2\right) \cos(\omega t), \quad (6)$$

where A_f is the amplitude of the forcing term, with a value of 0.8% of the free-stream velocity; x_c and y_c are the coordinates of the forcing strip; $s_y = \delta_c^*$ and $s_x = 2.5s_y$. The streamwise coordinate x_c is set to correspond to $Re_{\delta^*} = 700$ and $y_c = 1$, which places the actuator on the wall surface. The dimensionless circular frequency ω is defined as $\omega = Re_b F$, where F is the dimensionless frequency typically used in the characterization of T-S waves: $F = 2\pi f \nu / U_\infty^2$.

III. Results

A. Base flow without roughness element

A two-dimensional simulation of the “clean” flat plate geometry with super-elliptic leading edge, but without the roughness element, free-stream turbulence or T-S waves is carried out to assess the quality of the computational mesh, evaluate the development of the boundary layer flow, and define the location of the actuator x_c and discrete roughness element, which are based on the displacement thickness distribution.

Figure 4 shows the Reynolds number based on the displacement thickness distribution $\delta^*(x)$ corresponding to the numerical simulation, compared to the self-similar Blasius distribution. The presence of the leading edge leads to a departure of the flow from the self-similar one: first, the streamlines are curved following the super-ellipse until $x = 6$, which is the junction between the LE and the flat plate. The displacement thickness is only computed for $x > 6$. Second, the curvature of the streamlines and non-parallelism leads to a velocity maximum at the end of the boundary layer, that then reduces on the wall-normal direction towards the free-stream value. To take this into account, the boundary layer thickness is computed as:

Fig. 5 PSE results for T-S waves on the 2D boundary layer. **Left:** spatial growth rate $-\alpha_i$. **Right:** N -factor. The vertical dashed lines show the location of T-S actuator and the baseline DRE, for reference.

$$\delta^*(x) = \int_0^{y_{u,max}} \left(1 - \frac{U(x,y)}{U(x,y_{u,max})} \right) dy. \quad (7)$$

This definition converges monotonically towards the parallel-flow definition (where $y_{u,max} \rightarrow \infty$) as the boundary layer develops.

As shown by figure 4, the computed base flow has a small deviation from the Blasius self-similar solution. The actual Re_{δ^*} distribution is used to locate the actuator and the roughness elements. Following De Paula et al. [14], the actuator generating T-S waves is located at $Re_{\delta^*} = 700$, corresponding to $x_c = 65$, and the DRE at $Re_{\delta^*} = 920$, corresponding to $x = 115$. Based on the computed Re_{δ^*} distribution, the outlet boundary is placed at $L = 200$, to ensure a $Re_{\delta^*} \geq 1100$ at the end of the domain.

B. Amplification of T-S waves by the 2D boundary layer

Prior to the receptivity analysis involving free-stream turbulence and a DRE, PSE calculations are performed using a well-validated code [19, 20]. The calculations are initiated at $x = 6$, where the flat plate section starts, making it unnecessary to account for the wall curvature near the leading edge. The results for plane T-S waves are shown in figure 5. The left panel shows the spatial growth rate. Plane T-S waves are found to be linearly unstable already at $x = 6$, presumably as a consequence of the base flows streamlines curvature stemming from the leading edge geometry. This region of upstream instability is located well upstream the expected location of the first branch of the neutral curve for the Blasius boundary layer, that occurs around $Re_{\delta^*} \approx 500$ ($x \approx 30$ for the present flow), and for notably higher frequencies. This amplification rate is reduced one order of magnitude from $x = 6$ to $x = 65$, where the T-S actuator is located in the DNS set-up, and the unstable frequency range becomes considerably narrower and for lower frequencies, consistent with what is expected for a Blasius boundary layer.

The right panel in figure 5 shows the integrated amplification in terms of the N-factor:

$$N(x, \omega) = \int_{x_n}^x -\alpha_i(x', \omega) dx', \quad (8)$$

where x_n is the coordinate where the T-S wave becomes unstable for each ω . For those frequencies that are unstable at the beginning of the integration domain for PSE calculations, $x_n = 6$. The N-factor contours show that the high-frequency waves that are unstable near the leading edge are quickly damped downstream. Conversely, the comparatively lower frequencies that are typical of Blasius boundary layer instability remain amplified until the domain outlet.

Overall, the N-factor computed in this domain remains below $N = 2.5$, which corresponds to very small accumulated amplifications and are adequate for a study of the receptivity processes.

DNS calculations were performed including the plane T-S waves as perturbations of the Linearized Navier-Stokes equations convected downstream by the precomputed base flow.

Fig. 6 Slices of the perturbation fields obtained after the forcing of T-S waves with two temporal frequencies on the 2D boundary layer, showing the streamwise and the wall-normal components of the velocity for each frequency. **Top:** $F = 90 \times 10^{-6}$ ($\omega = 0.21$). **Bottom:** $F = 120 \times 10^{-6}$ ($\omega = 0.29$).

Fig. 7 Slice of the perturbation field for free-stream vortical disturbances at $F = 0$. **Top:** v' , **bottom:** w' .

The flow fields shown in figure 6 agree with the results of the PSE computations, as the amplitude of the wave with lower frequency $F = 90 \times 10^{-6}$ ($\omega = 0.21$) decays monotonically as it advances downstream, while the wave with higher frequency $F = 120 \times 10^{-6}$ ($\omega = 0.29$) grows continuously towards the domain outlet.

C. Receptivity of the 2D boundary layer to free-stream vortical disturbances

Fig. 8 Slice of the perturbation field for free-stream vortical disturbances at $F = 96 \times 10^{-6}$, $\omega = 0.23$. **Top:** v' , **bottom:** w' .

Preliminary simulations considering the flat-plate geometry without roughness element and a simplified model for the free-stream turbulence are carried out as validation and verification of the implementation. These simulations reproduce the cases reported by Schrader et al. [6]; the three-dimensional linearized Navier-Stokes equations are integrated in time using Nek5000, using the two-dimensional base flow described in the previous subsections.

The free-stream vortical disturbances are built using only seven streamwise-dominant vorticity modes for two

Fig. 9 Slice of the total streamwise velocity u' for free-stream vortical disturbances at $F = 0$ (top) and $F = 96 \times 10^{-6}$, $\omega = 0.23$ (bottom)

different non-dimensional frequencies, namely $F = 0$ and $F = 96 \times 10^{-6}$ ($\omega = 0.23$). The former is expected to penetrate in the boundary layer giving rise to streamwise streaks, while the latter, with a frequency in the range of the unstable T-S waves, is expected to trigger oblique T-S waves. Figures 7 and 8 show wall-normal and spanwise velocity fields at the half-span slices for the two frequencies.

The streamwise velocity component of the perturbation field, however, gives more information about the receptivity of the boundary layer depending of the frequency of the perturbations. Figure 9 gives a comparison between the disturbances triggered inside the boundary layer by the streamwise vorticity modes. Further post-processing treatment of the case with $F = 0$, based on [6], led to Fig. 10, where the steady streamwise free-stream vortices trigger disturbances into the boundary layer with a streaky pattern that resembles the initial states of evolution of the Klebanoff modes.

Fig. 10 Boundary-layer response to streamwise free-stream perturbations resulting from the addition of seven vorticity modes with $F = 0$. The surface represented corresponds to the wall-normal maximum of u'_{rms} and shows the value of disturbance streamwise velocity u' in that surface.

Fig. 11 Representation of the streamwise velocity component for the flow around the flat plate with a DRE at the reference location $x = 115$ and with the reference height ($k = 0.3\delta^*$). Top: slice of the complete domain. Bottom: zoomed view of the DRE.

D. Receptivity of the 2D boundary layer to a discrete roughness element and forced T-S waves

A new set of DNS calculations are carried out for cases including a DRE with two different roughness heights $k = 0.3\delta^*$ ($Re_{kk} = 50$) and $k = 0.5\delta^*$ ($Re_{kk} = 138$). The resulting flow field, represented in figure 11, serves as the base flow for computations with the Linearized Navier-Stokes equations where T-S waves are introduced as previously described.

The first simulation with this configuration is the reference case taken from [14], with a DRE height $k = 0.3\delta^*$ and a T-S wave at $F = 90 \times 10^{-6}$ ($\omega = 0.21$) frequency. A qualitative comparison between the flow field of the “clean” configuration and the case including a DRE, shown in figures 6 and 12 respectively, highlights a similar behavior of the planar wave for both cases, as the wave amplitude decays at very similar rates.

The next test cases consider a DRE with $k = 0.5\delta^*$ ($Re_{kk} = 138$) and the two relevant frequencies for the T-S wave excitation. The case with lower frequency compares well with the cases without the DRE, shown in figures 6 and 12. Conversely, the behaviour of the T-S wave at frequency $F = 90 \times 10^{-6}$ ($\omega = 0.21$) is significantly affected by the DRE, and the perturbation field of figure 13 now exhibits a sustained spatial growth, unlike the cases without DRE and with a DRE height of $k = 0.3\delta^*$ ($Re_{kk} = 50$).

The last case analysed increases the reference DRE height and shifts the wave frequency of the forced wave to $F = 120 \times 10^{-6}$ ($\omega = 0.29$). The perturbation fields in figure 14 show a growth comparable to the “clean” case, but downstream of the DRE the amplitude of the perturbations starts to decay up to the domain’s outlet.

Figure 15 shows the differences in the amplitudes of the perturbations for the cases of interest by comparing the envelope of the perturbations generated after a significant period of time. More precisely, the absolute value of the velocity components of the perturbations are retrieved from a straight line parallel to the flat plate geometry, with a wall-normal distance $y = 1.5\delta^*$ at the roughness element position. Afterwards, the maximum value for each x -coordinate position is normalized with a reference value taken at $x = 80$. The results are plotted to compare the effect over the

Fig. 12 Slices of the perturbation field obtained from the interaction of a T-S wave at frequency $F = 90 \times 10^{-6}$ ($\omega = 0.21$) with a DRE with height $k = 0.3\delta^*$. Top: streamwise velocity component. Bottom: wall-normal velocity component.

perturbation field of the reference frequencies and roughness element heights.

Focusing on the "clean" cases represented in 15, the T-S frequencies of interest have different evolution, as the case with $F = 90 \times 10^{-6}$ ($\omega = 0.21$) has an almost constant amplitude up to the region around $x \approx 100$, where a sharp decline in amplitude appears. On the other side, the frequency $F = 120 \times 10^{-6}$ ($\omega = 0.29$) grows gradually from $x \approx 100$ to the domain outlet, where it seems to stabilize. In the wall-normal velocity component, the amplitudes decay slightly for both frequencies, though at $F = 90 \times 10^{-6}$ ($\omega = 0.21$) the reduction is sharper downstream of $x \approx 100$.

The addition of a DRE with $k = 0.3\delta^*$ ($Re_{kk} = 50$) causes a slight and more gradual decrease of the amplitude for the lower frequency for both velocity components. However, the addition of the DRE with $k = 0.5\delta^*$ ($Re_{kk} = 138$) has a bigger impact, and changes the trend of the amplitudes for both frequencies. The T-S wave at $F = 120 \times 10^{-6}$ ($\omega = 0.29$) decreases in amplitude near the outlet, while at $F = 90 \times 10^{-6}$ ($\omega = 0.21$) it keeps growing exponentially.

E. Receptivity of the 2D boundary layer to isotropic free-stream turbulence

For the study of the receptivity of the boundary layer developed over the flat plate to isotropic free-stream turbulence, two test cases are considered, with the different turbulence intensities of $Tu = 0.03\%$ and $Tu = 0.3\%$. The turbulence spectrum described in section II introduces a broad range of wavenumbers in all three spatial directions. As shown by previous works in the literature, the vortical disturbances will penetrate in the boundary layer and excite a range of disturbances including the streaks shown in figure 10, precursors of Klebanoff modes, and also T-S waves. The instantaneous streamwise velocity component flow field is plotted in figure 16 for each of the Tu of interest.

The same analysis as for the case with T-S waves was done for the case with isotropic FST. First, showing the envelope of the components of the perturbations in figure 17. For these cases the reference value used to normalize the envelopes is taken at the streamwise position $x = 40$.

Under the "clean" configuration, the two turbulence intensities start growing at a similar rate and leave the domain

Fig. 13 Slices of the perturbation field obtained from the interaction of a T-S wave at frequency $F = 90 \times 10^{-6}$ ($\omega = 0.21$) with a DRE with height $k = 0.5\delta^*$. **Top: streamwise velocity component. Bottom: wall-normal velocity component.**

in similar conditions through quite different paths, although the amplitudes are generally bigger for $Tu = 0.03\%$.

The introduction of the DRE of $k = 0.5\delta^*$ ($Re_{kk} = 138$) seems to decrease the amplitude of the FST, particularly on the streamwise velocity component. Both velocity components keep the decay close to the outlet boundary.

IV. Conclusions

The simulations carried out during the present work served as a basis to establish a matrix of test cases that allowed the analysis of the receptivity of a two-dimensional boundary layer developed over a flat plate. The parameters under consideration for the analysis were the dimensionless circular frequency for the cases including a T-S actuator on the flat plate surface, the turbulence intensity of isotropic free-stream turbulence introduced in the domain as an inlet condition and the height of a DRE placed on the flat plate surface, at a reference streamwise location.

The preliminary results presented validated the numerical implementation and the approach to the problem through the response of the boundary layer developing over a flat plate with elliptic leading edge to free-stream vortical disturbances. They also served as a guide for the definition of the reference case (location and size of the discrete roughness element) and the matrix of cases to be simulated for the study of the receptivity of boundary layer disturbances to the combined effect of free-stream turbulence, leading edge and discrete roughness. More precisely, the PSE calculations made gave an initial estimation of the stability of the T-S waves developing over a base flow.

After the computation of a base flow, linearized N-S simulations were performed to solve the perturbation fields that include T-S waves or isotropic FST. From the analysis of the flow fields and the envelope of the perturbations generated by the T-S actuator, the evolution of the perturbations retrieved from the DNS agrees with the results of the PSE, since the smaller frequency, stable, lays close to the marginally stable region defined by the N -factor analysis and the high frequency shows a factor $N > 1$ at the actuator location. The addition of the higher DRE, with $k = 0.5\delta^*$ ($Re_{kk} = 138$),

Fig. 14 Slices of the perturbation field obtained from the interaction of a T-S wave at frequency $F = 120 \times 10^{-6}$ ($\omega = 0.29$) with a DRE with height $k = 0.5\delta^*$. **Top:** streamwise velocity component. **Bottom:** wall-normal velocity component.

Fig. 15 Envelope of the components of the perturbations generated by the forced T-S waves in different scenarios at a wall-distance $y = 1.5\delta_{DRE}^*$. The vertical dashed lines show the location of T-S actuator and the baseline DRE. **Left:** Envelope of the streamwise velocity A_u . **Right:** Envelope of the wall-normal velocity A_v .

Fig. 16 Slices of the streamwise velocity perturbation field obtained from the interaction between the isotropic FST and the two-dimensional boundary layer over the flat plate. **Top:** $Tu = 0.03\%$. **Bottom:** $Tu = 0.3\%$.

Fig. 17 Envelope of the components of the perturbations generated by the isotropic FST in different scenarios at a wall-distance $y = 1.5\delta_{DRE}^*$. **Left:** Envelope of the streamwise velocity A_u . **Right:** Envelope of the wall-normal velocity A_v .

destabilizes the perturbation field of both T-S cases, while the smaller DRE, with $k = 0.3\delta^*$ ($Re_{kk} = 50$), does not have an impact on the general behaviour of the flow field.

Finally, the addition of isotropic FST at the inflow of the "clean" case with very low values of Tu increases the amplitude of the perturbations in comparison with addition of the T-S actuator. In these scenarios, the presence of the DRE with $k = 0.5\delta^*$ ($Re_{kk} = 138$) plays an opposite role to the cases with T-S waves, as it stabilizes the perturbations shifting the sign of their growth rates and reducing their amplitudes in general.

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